

SELECTION AND CONTROL OF MANUFACTURING PROCESS VARIABLES FOR THERMOSET AND THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The role of models in manufacturing thermosetting and thermoplastic matrix composites is described. It is shown how models can be used to select the appropriate process variables, such as the applied heat and pressure during autoclave cure, the winding speeds, fiber tension and applied heat during filament winding, and the applied heating and cooling rates and pressures during the processing of thermoplastics. The use of computer models in choosing the process variables is outlined. The role of models as well as the use of expert systems in the real time control of the autoclave cure are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Structures made of fiber reinforced organic matrix composites are manufactured by many different methods, including autoclave curing, filament winding, sheet molding, injection molding, resin transfer molding, and pultrusion. Regardless which of these methods is used, care must be taken to employ the correct procedures during manufacture. Improper manufacturing procedures may result in parts which are of poor or unacceptable quality and are prohibitively expensive. To ensure that both the quality and the cost are acceptable, the manufacturing process must be tailored for each particular application. Specifically, it is important first to select the appropriate manufacturing conditions, and, second, to ensure that the desired conditions exist during the actual processing. These requirements necessitate that techniques be available for selecting and controlling the processing conditions.

The required conditions are established through variables which can and must be regulated during the processing. Temperature and pressure are two of the most important variables, and are common to the many different types of manufacturing processes. There are additional variables specific to different processes. For example, in filament winding the winding tension and winding speed, in molding and pultrusion the "feed" speed of the material into the mold or the dye must carefully be selected and controlled.

The aforementioned process variables can be chosen empirically. However, such an empirical approach is fraught with difficulties. Empirical, trial and error methods are expensive and time consuming, and do not guarantee that the resulting manufacturing conditions are optimum. It is far more advantageous and convenient to establish the required process conditions and process variables by rational approaches based on fundamental engineering principles. Two such approaches have been introduced in recent years, one utilizing analytic models, the other rule based expert systems.

In this paper a brief review is given of a) the existing models for autoclave curing and filament winding thermoset matrix composites, and for processing thermoplastic matrix composites, and b) the

application of expert systems to autoclave curing. It is noted that this paper is intended as an overview. The very long and complex mathematical analyses are not included here, because such details are beyond the scope of this paper. In the present summary the basic concepts are emphasized, and the methods for selecting and controlling the process variables are outlined. Readers interested in the analytical details are referred to the appropriate references.

AUTOCLAVE CURING THERMOSET MATRIX COMPOSITES

One of the most common ways of manufacturing parts made of high performance thermoset matrix composites is by autoclave curing. In the autoclave process, the part is formed into the desired shape and is placed in an autoclave (Fig. 1). Inside the autoclave heat and pressure are applied to the part. Heat accelerates the chemical reactions occurring during the cure, while the applied pressure squeezes out excess resin, compacts the plies, and reduces the void content. It is obvious that the durations and magnitudes of the applied temperatures and pressures (generally referred to as the cure cycle) affect significantly the quality of the part. Hence, these process variables must be chosen carefully. The requirements which must be satisfied during autoclave cure are summarized in Table 1.

The first model simulating the autoclave curing of composites was presented by Loos and Springer.^{1,2} This model consists of five submodels:

- 1) The "thermo-chemical" submodel yields the temperature, the degree of cure, and the viscosity.
- 2) The "flow" submodel gives the pressure, the resin flow out of the composite, and the resin contents of the composite and the bleeder.
- 3) The "void" submodel gives the void size.
- 4) The "stress" submodel yields the residual stresses.
- 5) The "strength" submodel gives the strength.

AUTOCLAVE

TEMPERATURE - PRESSURE

Figure 1. Illustration of the autoclave cure process.

The results of each of these submodels are summarized in Table 2 and in Fig. 2. Subsequent modifications to the flow model have been proposed by Gutowski and his co-workers^{3,4} and by Kardos et al.⁵ An alternate formulation to the Loos-Springer void model has been given by Kardos, Dave, and Dudukovic.⁶ The model was further extended by Campbell et al.⁷ to simultaneous curing of multiple parts in an autoclave.

Selection of the Process Variables

In order to facilitate the use of the Loos-Springer model in the selection of the process variables, the model was implemented by a user friendly computer code called "CURE". With this code the appropriate cure cycle can readily be determined by the following steps:

- 1) An arbitrarily chosen cure cycle (cure temperature and cure pressure) is entered into the code.
- 2) The results shown in Table 2 and in Fig. 2 are calculated and plotted.
- 3) The results are examined to see if all the conditions specified in Table 1 are satisfied.
- 4) If the conditions in Table 1 are not satisfied a new cure cycle is selected, and the procedure is repeated until all requirements are met. Generally, the required cure cycle is obtained within a few iterations.

The major steps of the aforementioned calculation procedure is best illustrated by the following example.

- 1) The temperature distribution is calculated as a function of time (Fig. 3). The temperature distribution should be uniform across the thickness of the composite and should not exceed a prescribed maximum value. Hence, the cure cycle resulting in temperatures shown in the left of Fig. 3 is unacceptable. Different cure cycles must be tried until the temperature history inside the material is as shown in the right of Fig. 3.

TABLE 1
CONDITIONS WHICH MUST BE MET DURING AUTOCLAVE CURING
AND FILAMENT WINDING OF COMPOSITES

- the temperature inside the material must not exceed a preset value at any time during the cure,
- at the end of the cure the resin content (and in case of filament winding the fiber tension) must be uniform and must have the desired value,
- the material must be cured uniformly and completely,
- the cured composite must have the lowest possible void content,
- the cured composite must have the desired thermal and mechanical properties,
- the curing must be achieved in the shortest time.

TABLE 2
SUMMARY OF THE INPUT PARAMETERS AND THE RESULTS
OF THE AUTOCLAVE CURE MODEL

Input Parameters

- 1) geometry,
- 2) material properties,
- 3) cure temperature as a function of time,
- 4) cure pressure as a function of time,
- 5) bleeder (vacuum bag) pressure as a function of time.

Results

Thermochemical Submodel

- 1) temperature inside the composite as function of position and time,
- 2) degree of cure of the resin as function of position and time,
- 3) resin viscosity as function of position and time.

Flow Submodel

- 4) pressure inside the composite as a function of position and time,
- 5) number of compacted prepreg plies as function of time,
- 6) amount of resin in the bleeder as function of time,
- 7) thickness and mass of the composite as function of time,
- 8) cure time.

Void Submodel

- 9) void sizes as functions of location and time.

Stress Submodel

- 10) residual stresses in each ply after cure.

Strength Submodel

- 11) strength and stiffness of the cured composite.

- 2) The degree of cure and viscosity distributions are plotted as a function of time (Fig. 4). Since these parameters depend on temperature, and since the temperature distribution is uniform as shown in the left of Fig. 3, the degree of cure and the viscosity will also vary uniformly across the material (Fig. 4).
- 3) The variation of viscosity with time is plotted (Fig. 5). From this plot the "cure window" (i.e., the viscosity region in which the material is still "soft") is established. If this cure window is too short or too long a new cure temperature is selected and the procedure, starting at step 1, is repeated.
- 4) The compaction as a function of time across the composite is plotted (Fig. 6). At the end of the cure process every ply must be compacted. Hence, a process leading to the compaction in the left of Fig. 6 is unacceptable. Another cure cycle must be chosen which ensures that compaction is complete across the entire laminate (Fig. 6, right). The rate at which compaction progresses is governed both by the cure temperature and the cure pressure. Therefore, the speed at which compaction takes place can be increased by changing either the cure temperature, the cure pressure, or both. If the rate of compaction is unacceptable, a new cure cycle is selected and the iteration is repeated starting at step 1.
- 5) The degree of cure versus time is plotted (Fig. 7). From this plot the cure time is determined. If this time is deemed too long, a new cure cycle is selected, and again the iteration is repeated starting at step 1.

In addition to the above steps, the cure cycle can further be optimized to provide the desired residual stresses and strains, strength, and void content. The procedure leading to the optimum values of these parameters is much the same as that given for the optimization of the temperature distribution, cure window, compaction, and cure time.

Figure 2. The results generated by the autoclave cure process simulation model (CURE code).

Figure 3. Typical temperature distributions across a laminate during autoclave cure. Temperature distributions on the left are unacceptable because of nonuniform temperatures and temperatures exceeding a prescribed maximum value.

Figure 4. Typical degree of cure and viscosity distributions across a laminate during autoclave cure.

Figure 5. Viscosity as a function of time during autoclave cure, and illustration of the cure window.

Figure 6. Compaction during autoclave cure of a laminate. Compaction on the left is unacceptable because not all the plies are compacted.

Figure 7. Degree of cure versus time during autoclave cure of a laminate.

FILAMENT WINDING THERMOSET MATRIX COMPOSITES

When a part is made by filament winding, fibers coated by a resin are wound on a mandrel (Fig. 8). To date, mostly thermoset matrix composites have been filament wound, although efforts are currently being made to filament wind thermoplastic matrix composites.

During winding the fibers are deposited on a suitably shaped mandrel by a crosshead which moves parallel to the axis of the mandrel. The angular speed of the mandrel ω and the crosshead speed V control the winding angle and the wind time. Thus, these process variables must be selected with care. In addition to the winding speeds, the fiber tension F_o must also be controlled during the wind. After the winding is complete the composite and mandrel assembly is placed in an oven, where the composite is cured. The temperature of the oven must also be selected with care. Thus, there are a total of five process variables (Table 3) which must be chosen prior to the manufacture and controlled during the manufacture, namely the

- a) mandrel geometry,
- b) mandrel angular velocity (ω),
- c) crosshead speed (V),
- d) initial fiber tension (F_o), and
- e) temperatures (T_m and T_s) or heat fluxes (q_m and q_s) at the inside surface of the mandrel and the outer surface of the composite cylinder (Fig. 8).

The process variables must be selected so as to satisfy all the conditions listed above in Table 1.

TABLE 3
SUMMARY OF THE INPUT PARAMETERS AND THE RESULTS
OF THE FILAMENT WINDING MODEL

Input Parameter

- 1) geometry,
- 2) material properties,
- 3) mandrel angular velocity,
- 4) crosshead speed,
- 5) initial fiber tension,
- 6) cure temperature.

Results

Thermo-chemical Submodel

- 1) temperature inside the composite and the mandrel as a function of position and time,
- 2) degree of cure of the resin as a function of position and time,
- 3) resin viscosity as a function of position and time,
- 4) cure time.

Flow Submodel

- 5) fiber position as a function of position and time,
- 6) fiber tension as a function of position and time,
- 7) resin and fiber distributions as a function of position and time,
- 8) thickness and mass of the composite as a function of time,
- 9) winding time.

Void Submodel

- 10) void sizes as functions of locations and time.

Stress Submodel

- 11) stresses and strains in each layer as function of time.

Strength Submodel

- 12) strength of the composite.

Figure 8. Illustration of the filament winding process.

A model recently proposed by Calius and Springer⁸⁻⁻¹⁰ can be used towards this end. This model consists of the same five submodels as the autoclave cure model, namely it consists of

- 1) the thermochemical submodel, which provides the temperature, degree of cure, viscosity, and the cure time,
- 2) the fiber motion submodel which yields the fiber positions and the resin distributions,
- 3) the stress submodel which results in the stresses and strains in the composite and the mandrel,
- 4) the void submodel which gives the porosity inside the composite, and
- 5) the strength submodel which provides information regarding the strength of the cylinder.

It is emphasized that although the filament winding model resembles the autoclave cure model, the resemblance is superficial. The analyses in each submodel are significantly different for the filament winding and autoclave processes.

For a given set of the process variables, i.e., for given winding speed, fiber tension, and temperature history, the filament winding process model provides the following information as functions of positions and time

- temperature inside the composite and the mandrel,
- degree of cure inside the composite,
- viscosity inside the composite,
- fiber positions,
- fiber tensions,
- stresses and strains inside the composite and the mandrel,
- void diameters (porosity) inside the composite,
- winding and cure times.

The detailed results (output) provided by the model as well as the input parameters required by the model are summarized in Table 3 and in Fig. 9.

Selection of the Process Variables

To facilitate the calculations the Calius-Springer model has also been implemented with a "user-friendly" computer code called "WIND". This code can be used to determine the filament winding process variables in much the same way as the CURE code can be used in autoclave curing. Following the detailed procedure described in the previous section, a set of process variables, selected arbitrarily, are entered into the code. The results given by the code are examined. The input parameters are then changed and the process is repeated until all the results satisfy the conditions in Table 1.

PROCESSING THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

Processing of thermoplastic matrix composites consists of three major steps. First, matrix is introduced into the space between the fibers in each tow, "impregnating" the tow (Fig. 10). Second, individual plies are "consolidated" such that there is good contact as well as good bond between the fibers. Third, the composite is heated and then cooled at a rate which provides the desired "crystallinity" in the matrix.

The aforementioned processes have been described by a model which consists of three submodels. These submodels correspond to the three processing steps of impregnation, consolidation, and crystallinity. A model encompassing all three submodels has been presented by Lee and Springer.¹¹ Submodels pertaining only to consolidation have been proposed by Dara and Loos.¹² Submodels representing the crystallization process have been developed, among others, by Lee et al.¹³ and Seferis and Velisaris.¹⁴⁻⁻¹⁵

Figure 9. The results generated by the filament winding process simulation model (WIND code).

Figure 10. Impregnation of a fiber tow with thermoplastic matrix.

Figure 11. Top: Consolidation of uneven surfaces of thermoplastic matrix laminates. Bottom: Model of the consolidation process.

Impregnation is done either by the material supplier (manufacturer) during preparation of prepreg fibers, plies, or laminates, or by the user during "in situ" fabrication of laminates and parts. Impregnation is accomplished by surrounding the tow with the matrix and heating the tow-matrix system to a temperature at which the matrix becomes capable of penetrating into the spaces between the fibers. The Lee-Springer "impregnation" submodel provides 1) the depth to which the matrix penetrates in a given time, and 2) the time required to completely fill (impregnate) the tow with the matrix.

Consolidation consists of two phenomena. First, two adjacent ply surfaces coalesce and come into "intimate contact" (Fig. 11). Second, bond forms at the ply interface. This bond formation can often be represented by a process called autohesion (Fig. 12). To facilitate intimate contact heat and pressure are applied to the composite. To achieve good bonding heat is applied to the material. The submodels pertaining to the consolidation processes relate the applied heat and pressure to the degree of intimate contact and to the degree of bonding, and provide the time required to reach the required levels of intimate contact and bonding for given processing conditions (i.e., for given heat and pressure).

For semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix composites the degree of crystallinity is achieved by cooling the composite from the melt temperature at an appropriate cooling rate. The submodels proposed in the past for the crystallization process relate the cooling rate applied during processing to the crystallinity of the material.

The input parameters required, and the results provided by the various submodels are listed in Table 4 and Fig. 13.

Selection of the Process Variables

The Lee-Springer model has also been implemented by a "user-friendly" ready-to-use computer code designated as PLASTIC. This code can be used to establish the appropriate process variables, namely the heating and cooling rates and pressures which need to be applied during the manufacture of thermoplastic matrix composites. The procedure for selecting the process variables is similar to the one used with the CURE and WIND codes. A set of process variables are entered into the code. The results generated for these variables are examined. The calculations are repeated until the process variables are such that the conditions given in Table 5 are met.

Figure 12. Autohesion during processing of thermoplastic matrix composites.

Figure 13. The results generated by the thermoplastic process simulation model (PLASTIC code).

Figure 14. Illustration of the model based control of the autoclave cure process.

TABLE 4

**SUMMARY OF THE INPUT PARAMETERS AND THE RESULTS
OF THE THERMOPLASTIC PROCESS MODEL**

Input Parameter

- 1) geometry,
- 2) material properties,
- 3) heating rate as a function of time,
- 4) cooling rate as a function of time,
- 5) pressure as a function of time.

Results

Impregnation Submodel

- 1) degree of impregnation as a function of time,
- 2) time required to reach full impregnation.

Consolidation Submodel

- 3) degree of intimate contact as a function of time,
- 4) time required to achieve complete intimate contact,
- 5) degree of autohesion as a function of time,
- 6) time required to achieve full autohesion,
- 7) degree of bonding as a function of time,
- 8) time required to achieve full bonding.

Crystallinity Submodel

- 9) crystallinity of the matrix as a function of position and time,
- 10) crystallinity of the matrix as a function of position at the end of the manufacturing process,
- 11) mechanical properties of the material at the end of the manufacturing process.

CONTROL OF THE CURING PROCESS

Once the appropriate processing conditions have been selected, it must be ensured that these conditions are maintained during the entire curing process. Furthermore, it is insufficient just to preselect the controls, they must also be adjusted continuously to account for unexpected variations in material properties and in processing conditions. The former may be due to "batch to batch" variations in the material. The latter may be caused by unexpected changes in the applied pressure or in the power supply (e.g., power black out). Hence, the controls must not only be set according to a preassigned schedule but must be adjusted in real time.

The cure process may be controlled in one of two ways, either by the use of deterministic models or by rule based expert systems. Each of these methods is discussed in the following. First however, the sensor technology needed to effect the control is discussed briefly.

For sensitive, real time control of the curing process it would be necessary to monitor continuously the following parameters

- a) temperature at different positions inside the composite,
- b) viscosity at different positions inside the composite,
- c) degree of cure at different positions inside the composite,
- d) resin flow in different directions and at different positions,
- e) thickness of the composite at different positions,
- f) residual strains at different positions inside the composite,
- g) void content at different positions inside the composite.

Of these seven parameters only one, the temperature, can now readily be measured. Measurements of the other six parameters pose great difficulties. In fact, to date, commercial instruments are only available for measuring the viscosity and the degree of cure (e.g., see References 16-25). Even these instruments, based on the measurements of dielectric properties of the resin, cannot-as yet-provide absolute values of either the viscosity or the degree of cure. Typically, these instruments can only indicate the times at which the viscosity is minimum and at which the cure is near completion.

The control strategies discussed below assume that all the required sensors listed above are available. Since this is not yet the case, full implementation of these control strategies will have to await the maturation of the sensor technology.

1. Model Based Control

Models such as described in the previous sections (e.g., CURE, WIND) can be used to control the curing process. The method of control is illustrated by the schematic in Fig. 14. The major steps of the control process are

- 1) The processing conditions and the values of the process variables (cure temperature, cure pressure) are determined prior to the manufacture using the appropriate model.
- 2) For the selected process conditions the parameters of interest inside the material are calculated as functions of position and time. These may include all seven parameters listed above or only some of these parameters (e.g., temperature, viscosity, or degree of cure), as shown in Fig. 14.
- 3) The calculated values of the parameters are stored in a computer.
- 4) The parameters of interest are measured by appropriate sensors located inside the material.
- 5) The measured values of the parameters are also fed into the computer, and are compared with the precalculated values.

TABLE 5

CONDITIONS WHICH MUST BE MET
DURING PROCESSING THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

- the tows must be fully impregnated,
- the individual plies must be in complete intimate contact,
- the bonds between individual plies must be complete,
- the crystallinity must have the desired value throughout the composite.

- 6) If the measured and precalculated values do not match then, using again the model, a new set of process conditions are calculated which result in the required material properties. The controls are then reset according to the results of these calculations.

Steps 1-6 above are to be performed in real time.

As indicated in Fig. 14, "models" are needed also to convert the sensor signals to absolute values of the parameters. The reason for this is that the sensors only yield electric signals. Models (or some form of calibration) are necessary to interpret these signals and to attach physical meanings to them. In fact, our lack of knowledge of how fully to interpret these signals is the major reason why we cannot measure in real time the absolute values of viscosity and degree of cure, and cannot apply the aforementioned control strategy to the curing process.

2. Rule Based Control

Controls based on models require that the material properties (which are to be entered into the model) be known. These properties are difficult to determine. Furthermore, as noted in the foregoing, some of the properties may change prior to or during processing. In contrast to model based controls, rule based control strategies have the advantage that they do not require any knowledge of the properties.

The first rule based control strategy for curing composites was developed recently by Abrams and his coworkers at the Air Force Materials Laboratory.²⁶ The ingenious method proposed by these investigators promises to lead to economical and practical manufacturing of composites by autoclave curing. The control method suggested by Abrams et al. can best be illustrated by the following simple example.

The temperatures are monitored at three locations: on the surface of the composite (T_s , Fig. 15), at the center of the composite (T_c), and inside the autoclave (T_a). The autoclave temperature is controlled then according to the following two simple rules.

- 1) If the center temperature is less than the surface temperature ($T_c < T_s$)
and
if the surface temperature is less than an allowed maximum value ($T_s < T_{max}$),
then
increase the autoclave temperature T_a .
- 2) If the center temperature is greater than the surface temperature ($T_c > T_s$)
or
if the surface temperature is greater than an allowed maximum value ($T_s > T_{max}$),
then
decrease the autoclave temperature T_a .

It is emphasized that the above rules are grossly oversimplified and merely serve as a demonstration of the idea. In practice, more than two thermocouples are required and more than two rules must be employed to achieve good cure. Indeed, engineers at the Air Force Materials Laboratory already have extended the method to cures using multiple thermocouples, and demonstrated that a part cured by such a method has acceptable mechanical properties.

Although rule based control strategies offer great possibilities, in order to make these strategies viable other parameters besides temperature will need to be measured, and (in addition to the cure temperature) the cure pressure also will need to be controlled. As discussed previously, the sensors required for this purpose have not yet been developed. Full utilization of rule based control methods will have to await the availability of the proper sensors.

EXAMPLE

IF $T_C < T_S$
 AND $T_S < T_{max}$ INCREASE T_A

IF $T_C > T_S$
 OR $T_S > T_{max}$ DECREASE T_A

Figure 15. Illustration of the rule based control of the autoclave cure process.

CONCLUDING REMARK

The models referred to in this paper simulate well the processing of thermoset and thermoplastic matrix composites. These models are most useful in establishing the process variables which should be applied in a given problem. These models are especially useful and important for manufacturing large and thick composites, where empirical methods cannot provide the optimum processing conditions.

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